

Incidence of bacterial blight of rice in the Punjab (Pakistan)

Waseem Ahmad, assistant research officer (Plant Pathology), and Abdul Majid, director, Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan

Bacterial blight of rice caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* is not generally found in Pakistan, but Mew et al reported its occurrence during 1976 kharif in the rice fields of Kala Shah Kaku, Punjab [IRRN 2 (1) (1977)]. In 1980 because of heavy monsoon rains and frequent windstorms, the pathogen has reappeared. Its incidence was observed

in the experimental fields of the Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, and in farmers' fields. The disease was noted on the rice varieties IR6, Palman, and Basmati 198. Infected leaf samples were examined microscopically, and the bacterial ooze at the junction of the infected and healthy parts of the cut leaves was observed.

Among the various climatic factors that favor the development of bacterial blight, temperature and humidity seem to be more important.

During July-August 1976, the amount of rainfall was 413 mm and the weather remained cloudy most of the time. The

appearance of the disease was recorded under such weather conditions. In July-August 1980, rainfall was 886.3 mm and the weather was similar to that in 1976. The disease seems to flourish in highly humid and cloudy conditions.

During 1980, windstorms frequently accompanied rain showers and the injury they caused on the leaves provided openings for the entrance of the pathogen.

During the infection period, the temperature ranged from 25 to 32 ± 1°C, which is highly conducive to the spread of the disease. ■

Fungicidal control of sheath blight

V. Viswanathan and V. Mariappan, Plant Pathology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India

The efficiency of fungicides applied as prophylactic and therapeutic sprays and as soil drench in the control of sheath blight disease was studied. The variety ADT31 sown in pots was fertilized with 120-6040 kg N-P-K/ha. The fungicides carbendazim (0.01%), carboxin (0.01%), Kitazin (0.02%), Panolil (0.02%), Syllit (0.02%), Mancozeb (0.02%), and Daconil (0.02%) were sprayed on the plants as protective and curative treatments. For the prophylactic treatment the fungicides were sprayed on 60-day-old plants. Two days later the plants were inoculated with the pathogen by the pinprick method (2-3 pin-pricks/plant on the leaf sheath 6-10 cm above the water level). Sclerotia were immediately applied on the pricked surface and covered with moist cotton. For the therapeutic treatment, the 60-day-old plants were inoculated; 2 days later the fungicides were sprayed. For drenching, carbendazim (0.01%), carboxin (0.01%), wet Ceresan (0.01%), and PCNB (0.01%) were applied to the soil of the 60-day-old plants immediately after inoculation. The control was plants inoculated with the pathogen but not protected with fungicides. Each treatment had three replications. Ten days after inoculation, disease incidence was recorded and disease severity (0-9

Table 1. Percentage of disease index (PDI) when fungicides were applied as prophylactic and therapeutic sprays. Coimbatore, India.

Fungicide sprayed	PDI value ^a	
	Prophy-lactic spray	Thera-peutic spray
Carbendazim (0.01%)	24.92	25.49
Carboxin (0.01%)	26.08	27.08
Kitazin (0.01%)	27.09	28.09
Panolil (0.027%)	49.07	49.49
Syllit (0.02%)	42.67	44.81
Mancozeb (0.02%)	49.49	50.77
Daconil (0.02%)	40.51	40.51
Control (no fungicide)	54.75	55.66

^aTransformed values. Mean of 3 replications.

S.E.D. = 1.30 1.06

C.D. = 2.80 2.28

(P = 0.05% level)

Table 2. Percentage of disease index (PDI) when fungicides were applied as soil drench. Coimbatore, India.

Fungicide used for drenching	PDI value ^a
Carbendazim (0.01%)	27.72
Carboxin (0.01%)	27.72
Wet Ceresan (0.01%)	29.17
PCNB (0.01%)	28.47
Control (no fungicide)	58.33

^aTransformed values. Mean of 3 replications.

S.E.D. = 1.48; C.D. = 3.23 at P = 0.05% level.

scale) was determined. The percentage of the disease index (PDI) was determined:

$$PDI = \frac{\text{total ratings} \times 100}{\text{no. of tillers} \times \text{maximum grade}}$$

Both as prophylactic and therapeutic spray, carbendazim, carboxin, and Kitazin most effectively controlled the

disease (Table 1). As soil drench, carbendazim, carboxin, wet Ceresan, and PCNB were equally effective (Table 2). Both carbendazim and carboxin, however, were effective as a spray and as a drench. ■

Effect of nitrogen and spacing on sheath blight incidence in rice

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai 612101 Tamil Nadu, India

In a fertilization-spacing trial conducted during 1979 kuruvai, the incidence of sheath blight was assessed. There were 4 spacings (10 x 10, 20 x 20, 30 x 30, and 40 x 40 cm) and 4 levels of nitrogen (0, 50, 100, and 200 kg/ha) applied as full basal, 2 splits (75 + 25%), 3 splits (50 + 25 + 25%), and 4 splits (40 + 20 + 20 + 20%). Phosphorus and potassium were applied at 98% sufficiency level of the field. Data on sheath blight incidence are in the table.

With zero nitrogen, there was no disease incidence at all spacings.

With 50 kg N/ha, disease incidence ranged from 16.2 to 21.6% for the 10- x 10-cm spacing and 1.8 to 2.7% for 20 x 20 cm. No incidence was noted at the 30- x 30- and 40- x 40-cm spacings. With 100 kg N/ha, disease incidence was 49.5-59.4% for the 10- x 10-cm spacing, 4.5-6.3% for 20 x 20 cm and only 0.7-1.0% at 30 x 30 and 40 x 40 cm.

With 200 kg N/ha, disease incidence was 53.1-60.3% for the 10-x 10-cm.